

Studies on Antitubercular Agents. Part II : Preparation of Some 2-alkyl/aryl/arylalkyl/ cycloalkyl/heterocyclylamino-4-(2- or 4-ethoxy- anilino)-6-(isonicotinylhydrazino)-s-Triazine

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THE isoniazid feature has been the subject of several investigations in the realm of potential therapeutic agents for *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. The molecular modifications of this specific antimycobacterial agent revealed that 2-alkyl/arylalkyl/heterocyclyl (-CONHNHR) derivatives had high *in vivo* activity¹⁻⁷. Despite this, many s-triazine derivatives have potential therapeutic activity⁸⁻¹². In light of this some 2-alkyl/aryl/heterocyclyl amino-4-ethoxyanilino-6-isonicotinylhydrazino-s-triazines have been prepared and tested against H₃₇R_v strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*.

Ar = 4-Ethoxyphenyl M.P. 158 ; 2-Ethoxyphenyl M.P. 148 ;
R = Different aminoresidues.

Experimental

Preparation of 2,4-dichloro-6-(2 or 4-ethoxyanilino)-s-triazine :

Cyanuric chloride (0.01 mole) and ethoxyaniline (0.01 mole) were separately dissolved in acetone and mixed at 0°. To it, NaOH (aqueous 4% ; 100 ml) was added dropwise, stirred at 0-5° for 3 hrs and the contents poured on crushed ice, rendered acidic (HCl) to congo-red, filtered and crystallised from ethylacetate.

Preparation of 2-chloro-4-(2 or 4-ethoxyanilino)-6-(isonicotinylhydrazino)-s-triazine :

Isonicotinic acid hydrazide (0.08 mole) and 2,4-dichloro-6-(ethoxyanilino)-s-triazine (0.08 mole) were dissolved separately in dioxane and mixed at 10-15°. This was followed by the dropwise addition of NaHCO₃ (1M, 90 ml) and stirring at 30-35° for 3 hrs. The contents poured on crushed ice, rendered acidic (HCl) to congo-red and filtered, the product so obtained washed repeatedly with water and recrystallised from ethanol (95%).

Preparation of 2-alkyl/aryl/heterocyclylamino-4-(2 or 4-ethoxyanilino)-s-triazine :

An amine (0.002 mole) and 2-chloro-4-(ethoxyanilino)-6-(isonicotinylhydrazino)-s-triazine (0.002 mole) were taken in dioxane and refluxed for 1½ hr with the simultaneous dropwise addition of aq. NaHCO₃ (10% 2 ml). The contents poured on ice,

filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol (95%). The physical data, m.p., yield etc. are given in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—SUBSTITUTED-4-(4-ETHOXYANILINO)-6-ISONICOTINYLHYDRAZINO-S-TRIAZINE

No.	R	Yield %	m.p.°C	Minimal inhibition concentration µg/ml
1.	Chloro	97.6	263	1.6
2.	Anilino	93.9	291	3.2
3.	2-Chloroanilino	95.5	289	3.2
4.	3-Chloroanilino	93.4	304	3.2
5.	4-Chloroanilino	93.4	298	3.2
6.	2,5-Dichloroanilino	92.9	279	—
7.	p-Anisidino	95.8	218	3.2
8.	p-Phenitidino	95.7	296	3.2
9.	p-Bromoanilino	96	300(d)	—
10.	2-Pyridylamino	92.5	296(d)	—
11.	Piperidino	94.5	316(d)	—
12.	Morpholino	92.8	306(d)	3.2
13.	dl-α-Phenethylamino	93.6	287	3.2
14.	dl-α-p-Chlorophenethylamino	91.2	271-72	3.2
15.	dl-α-p-Methoxyphenethylamino	92	296	3.2
16.	dl-α-p-Tolylethylamino	96	295	3.2
17.	Dimethylamino	95.2	268	3.2
18.	Diethylamino	96	266	3.2
19.	Cyclohexylamino	93.7	280	—
20.	n-Butylamino	94.8	238	—
21.	Benzylamino	94.3	274	—

All the above compounds gave correct N analysis.
Incubation period 21 days at 36°.

TABLE 2—SUBSTITUTED-4-(2-ETHOXYANILINO)-6-ISONICOTINYLHYDRAZINO-S-TRIAZINE

No.	R	Yield %	m.p.°C	Minimal inhibition concentration µg/ml
1.	Cl	97.9	238	1.6
2.	Anilino	93.9	267	3.2
3.	2-Chloroanilino	94.4	279	3.2
4.	3-Chloroanilino	93.4	302(d)	3.2
5.	4-Chloroanilino	93.4	298	3.2
6.	2,5-Dichloroanilino	92.9	296	—
7.	p-Anisidino	95.8	298	3.2
8.	p-Phenitidino	95.7	273	3.2
9.	p-Bromoanilino	96	273	—
10.	2-Pyridylamino	92.5	298(d)	—
11.	Piperidino	94.5	282	—
12.	Morpholino	94	269	3.2
13.	α-Phenethylamino	91.5	275	3.2
14.	α-p-Chlorophenethylamino	89.2	304(d)	—
15.	α-p-Methoxyphenethylamino	94	276	—
16.	Dimethylamino	96.4	230(d)	3.2
17.	Diethylamino	96	269	3.2
18.	Cyclohexylamino	93.7	266	3.2
19.	n-Butylamino	94.8	262	3.2
20.	Benzylamino	94.3	282(d)	3.2

All the above compounds gave correct N analysis.
Incubation period 21 days at 36°.

The *in vitro* antitubercular activity of the 2-alkyl/aryl/arylalkyl/heterocyclylamino-4-(ethoxyanilino)-6-isonicotinylhydrazino-s-triazine have been carried out against H₃₇R_v strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* using Lowenstein-Jensen egg medium. It has

been found that minimal inhibition concentration (MIC) decreases with increasing molecular weight.

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Preparation of β -aryl, γ -aroyl Butyric Acids : the Attempted Synthesis of Hydantoin Analogues

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HENZ and Leslie¹ have synthesised a number of 5,5-disubstituted hydantoin from ketones by Bucherer-Berg reaction. Even though they synthesised β -(5-aryl hydantoin 5-) propionic acid from acrylophenone, Deshpande and Nargund² described a shorter route to β -(5-aryl hydantoin 5-) propionic acids starting from β -aroyl propionic acids and also reported their activity as antituberculosis agents. Analogous to this, synthesis of β -aryl γ -(5-aryl hydantoin 5-) butyric acids were attempted. Hence the preparation of β -aryl γ -aroyl butyric acids were taken up as intermediate compounds.

Earlier many workers^{3,4,5} have reported the synthesis of simple β -phenyl γ -benzoyl butyric acid by

different methods, synthesis of β -aryl, γ -aroyl butyric acids having substituents in aromatic rings have not been reported. In the present investigation, procedure for β -aryl, γ -aroyl butyric acids is standardised and fifteen new γ -keto acids are reported (Table 1).

TABLE I

No.	R ₁	R ₂	R	I		II	
				m.p.°C	Yield%	m.p.°C	
1.	H	H	H	57.0 ⁹	35.9	155.0	
2.	H	H	CH ₃	—	—	102.0	
3.	H	CH ₃	H	96 ⁹	97.4	133.0	
4.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	—	—	92.0	
5.	H	OCH ₃	H	77-78 ¹⁰	32.7	124.0	
6.	H	OCH ₃	CH ₃	—	—	89.5	
7.	H	Cl	H	103-104 ¹¹	27.9	158.0	
8.	H	Cl	CH ₃	—	—	132.0	
9.	CH ₃	H	H	74.0 ⁹	39.7	164.5	
10.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	—	—	131.0	
11.	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	127.5 ⁹	41.2	122.0	
12.	CH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	—	—	78.0	
13.	CH ₃	OCH ₃	H	94.0 ⁹	35.2	105.0	
14.	CH ₃	OCH ₃	CH ₃	—	—	67.5	
15.	CH ₃	Cl	H	122.5 ¹²	26.1	137.0	
16.	CH ₃	Cl	CH ₃	—	—	95.0	
17.	OCH ₃	H	H	106.0 ¹³	41.5	149.0	
18.	OCH ₃	H	CH ₃	—	—	104.0	
19.	OCH ₃	CH ₃	H	126.0 ¹⁴	37.2	126.0	
20.	OCH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	—	—	97.5	
21.	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	H	101-102 ¹⁵	29.4	137.0	
22.	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	CH ₃	—	—	111.5	
23.	OCH ₃	Cl	H	121.0 ¹⁶	24.3	127.0	
24.	OCH ₃	Cl	CH ₃	—	—	94.5	
25.	Cl	H	H	101 ¹⁷	26.8	143.0	
26.	Cl	H	CH ₃	—	—	116.0	
27.	Cl	CH ₃	H	165 ¹⁸	25.5	132.0	
28.	Cl	CH ₃	CH ₃	—	—	113.5	
29.	Cl	OCH ₃	H	130 ¹⁶	26.1	138.0	
30.	Cl	OCH ₃	CH ₃	—	—	108.0	
31.	Cl	Cl	H	134 ¹⁶	21.2	156.0	
32.	Cl	Cl	CH ₃	—	—	129.0	

Note : All the compounds have given satisfactory C, H and Cl (wherever required) analysis. The analyses were carried out at NCL (Microanalysis Group), Pune-8.

Various chalcones⁶(I) were prepared having different substituents in both the aromatic rings at para positions and subjected to Michael addition of diethyl malonate (ME). The resulting diesters were hydrolysed, without purification and decarboxylated to obtain β -aryl, γ -aroyl butyric acids(II). They were identified by elemental estimation and infrared spectroscopy (aromatic carbonyl: 1685 cm⁻¹-1665 cm⁻¹, carboxyl carbonyl: 1720 cm⁻¹-1705 cm⁻¹)⁷ and confirmed by preparing their esters which are also identified by their elemental analysis (Table 1). The acids were subjected to Bucherer-Berg reaction but failed to yield hydantoin derivatives(III) (Fig. 1). More polar solvents and changed reaction conditions was also a failure. Cause of non-formation of five membered hydantoin ring may be the steric hindrance of bulky β -aromatic substitution,